

mains. The liquid inside the tube is taken out and is found to give positive test with Nessler's reagent. The tube is repeatedly filled up with distilled water, electrolysis continued, and the solution from inside the tube withdrawn. Ammonia is detected in the solution every time. On titrating with acid solution, the strength of the solution after overnight electrolysis is found to be about $10^{-2}N$. At a slightly higher temperature (ca 40°) the formation of ammonia increases to some extent but no trace of ammonia could be detected on increasing the strength of the acid solution at the anode side i.e., outside the cathode tube.

Fig. 1

Secondly, a U-tube (32 mm O.D) is taken instead of the beaker and the electrolysis is carried out without keeping the cathode within the cellophane covered tube. Ammonia formation does not take place at all but as soon as the cathode is placed inside the cellophane covered glass tube (Fig. 2),

Fig. 2

measurable amount of ammonia is formed after electrolysis for 24 hr. So in essence, ammonia could be produced irrespective of the cell used

provided the cathode is kept separated from the rest of the electrolyte by a narrow glass tube the bottom end of which is covered by a cellophane membrane.

Since the reduction of nitrogen to ammonia in the above set ups is greater with dilute solution and since electrolysis of such dilute solutions gives rise to non-Faradaic electrolysis, there is probably something in common for the genesis of these two phenomena. Since hydrated electron formation near the cathode is one of the suggested explanations of non-Faradaic electrolysis⁵, it may be assumed that a steady state concentration of hydrated electrons builds up inside the cathode chamber. This is theoretically possible because electrons are being pumped in at the rate of about 10^{16} electrons/sec at about 1 mA whereas the hydrated electrons get annihilated at a rate constant of the order of 10^9 - 10^{11} /sec⁶. So the cathode chamber after sometimes becomes a veritable storehouse of electrons and this almost instantaneous build-up of electrons is responsible for the observed reduction of dissolved nitrogen to ammonia. This mechanism has also been considered to be responsible for the current increasing effect of cellophane membranes⁷.

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Utilisation of Indian Turpentine : Catalysed Conversion of Δ^8 -Carene to *p*- and *m*-Cymene over Platinum-Alumina

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INDIAN turpentine has not been exploited to the fullest extent. A major difficulty in its utilization is the presence of 3-carene to the extent of about 60%, which gets easily oxidised in air with resin formation¹. Consequently, the oil cannot be stored

for long as an industrial raw material. It is used presently as thinner for paints and varnishes. Attempts are being made to convert this unstable material into a mixture of *p*- and *m*-cymenes over chromia and chromia-alumina catalysts²⁻⁴.

Though chromia and chromia-alumina have been widely used as effective aromatization catalysts, their maximum efficiency occurs in the high temperature regions, i.e., around 500°. In this temperature range the catalysts are prone to undergo sintering and hence a loss of activity. On the other hand, platinum when dispersed over a support like alumina brings about aromatization at a comparatively lower temperature range of 250-350°. In this work the dehydrogenation of 3-carene to *p*- and *m*-cymenes has been investigated over platinum-alumina and platinum-alumina modified with cesium and fluoride ions catalysts at different temperatures.

A mixture of *p*- and *m*-cymenes can be oxidised to tere-, and iso-phthalic acids respectively⁵ (since iso-phthalic acid is soluble in hot water, the acid mixture can be separated by hot water treatment). *p*-Cymene can also be hydrated to camphor⁶ and converted to *p*-cresol⁶ via its hydroperoxide. Verghese has reviewed the important applications of *p*-cymene⁷.

Experimental

Preparation of catalysts :

Platinum-alumina :

Alumina was prepared by hydrolysing aluminium isopropoxide (B.D.H., A.R.) according to the method of Pines *et al.*⁸. Platinum-alumina catalysts A, B, C, D and E were obtained by adding calculated volumes of chloroplatinic acid solution in water to five weighed samples of alumina to give respectively 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9 and 1.4% platinum by weight (confirmed by spectrophotometric analysis⁹). The slurry was stirred for 3 hr and dried at 120° for 24 hr. The temperature was then raised slowly while passing pure dry hydrogen to reach 500° in 2 hr and kept at this temperature for 8 hr. The activated material was powdered and sieved to 16-30 mesh size particles.

Platinum-alumina modified with hydrofluoric acid (catalysts F and G) :

Catalysts F and G were prepared by impregnating platinum-alumina catalyst C with appropriate volumes of hydrofluoric acid (40% solution, E Merck) to give respectively 5 and 10% by weight of hydrogen fluoride in the catalyst. The particle size of the catalyst was in the range 16-30 mesh.

Platinum-alumina doped with cesium oxide (catalysts H, I and J) :

Catalysts H, I and J were obtained by doping catalyst C with requisite volumes of cesium nitrate solution in water to give respectively 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5% by weight of Cs⁺ in the catalyst. The particle size in these cases was also 16-30 mesh. The procedure described earlier was followed for drying and activation.

3-Carene :

Top quality Indian turpentine, supplied by the Government Turpentine and Rosin Company Ltd., Bareilly, India, containing about 50% 3-carene (b.p. 170°), 40% α -pinene (b.p. 156°) and 10% β -pinene (b.p. 165°) was used to obtain 3-carene by fractionation in a 152 cm glass column packed with ceramic beads equivalent to 20 theoretical plates at a reduced pressure of 10 mm Hg. The purity of 3-carene was found to be more than 99% by gas chromatographic analysis.

Other details of the experimental procedure and analysis of the products were the same as described earlier^{8,4,10}.

Initial experiments conducted over oxidised and reduced catalysts did not show any significant variation in the product distribution. Therefore, all the runs in this investigation were conducted after activation of the catalysts in air, without reduction in hydrogen.

Results and Discussions

The effect of particle size on the conversion of 3-carene was studied by using catalyst C in the form of 4×4 mm pellets and 16-30 and 180-200 mesh particles. The amounts (mole%) of 3-carene converted at 300° and at contact time 0.79 hr were 96.4, 99.4 and 99.8%, respectively, indicating that the particle size has little effect on the reaction. The amounts (mole%) of cymenes formed during the time intervals 0-30, 31-45 and 46-60 min over catalyst D were 63.1, 63.3 and 63.4%, respectively, which shows that the catalyst maintains constant activity during the reaction period.

The conversion of 3-carene does not show much variation with varying platinum concentration (Table I), since the isomerizing action of the catalyst is associated with alumina and not with platinum metal sites. On the other hand, increase in the concentration of platinum upto 0.6% increases the dehydrogenation and disproportionation of menthadienes to cymenes, menthanes and menthenes thereby decreasing the concentration of the former and increasing that of the latter (Table I). Further increase of platinum concentration beyond 0.6% has no beneficial effects.

Platinum upto 0.6% could be dispersed well over alumina. Over the exposed metal surface the menthadienes adsorb strongly, as they are highly unsaturated reactive intermediates and undergo dehydrogenation and disproportionation. Further increase in platinum concentration might affect the dispersion of platinum by crystallite formation which may decrease the activity of the metal component. Similar trend observed in the case of cyclohexane and cyclohexene¹⁰ confirms this. Sivasanker¹¹, while studying the adsorption of hydrogen over platinum-alumina catalysts, observed similar variation in the activity of the catalyst which was attributed by him to the increased crystallite size.

NOTES

TABLE 1

Composition (mole %)	Platinum concentration (wt. %)					Temperature (°C)			
	Temp. = 300° ; Contact time = 0.79 hr					Contact time = 0.79 hr ; Catalyst C			
	0.10	0.30	0.60	0.90	1.40	200	250	300	350
3-Carene unchanged	11.0	10.0	10.0	13.0	14.0	15.0	13.0	10.0	4.0
Menthadienes	37.0	28.0	3.0	10.0	26.0	6.4	7.0	3.0	1.0
Cymenes	44.0	53.0	75.0	67.0	52.0	60.0	63.0	75.0	83.0
Menthanes and menthenes	8.0	9.0	12.0	10.0	8.0	18.6	17.0	12.0	10.0

TABLE 2

	Cesium concentration (wt. %)				Hydrofluoric acid concentration (wt. %)		
	Contact time = 0.79 hr ; Catalyst C ; Temp. = 300°				Contact time = 0.79 hr ; Catalyst C ; Temp. = 300°		
	0	0.5	1.0	1.5	0	5	10
3-Carene unchanged	10.0	6.0	7.0	7.0	10.0	9.0	10.0
Menthadienes	3.0	6.0	15.0	18.0	3.0	29.0	33.0
Cymenes	75.0	78.3	70.0	69.0	75.0	56.0	52.0
Menthanes and menthenes	12.0	10.0	8.0	6.0	12.0	5.0	5.0

The effect of temperature on the rate of reaction as well as on the distribution of products is included in Table 1. The conversion of 3-carene increases with increasing temperature. The proportion of the intermediates, viz., the menthadienes, falls rapidly due to their further conversion to cymenes, menthanes and menthenes. Increase of temperature decreases the concentration of menthanes and menthenes also indicating the onset of their excessive dehydrogenation to cymenes, which appears to outweigh their formation.

The effect of cesium and fluoride ions on the reaction of 3-carene is given in Table 2. Addition of cesium brings about a small reduction in the conversion of 3-carene while hydrofluoric acid does not affect it. The increasing concentration of menthadienes with increasing cesium and fluoride ions is attributed to the reduction of the metal surface through blocking by these ions. As a result, the dehydrogenation and disproportionation activities of the catalyst diminish. To confirm this further, the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane and dehydrogenation and disproportionation of cyclohexene have been carried out over these modified catalysts. Here too, the reaction decreased with increasing concentrations of cesium and fluoride ions¹⁰.

Of the Cs⁺ and F⁻ ions, the latter decreases the formation of cymenes to a greater extent. Fluoride ions have been found to enhance the strength of acid sites¹². These strong sites may isomerise the six membered menthadienes to five membered alkyl cyclopentadienes as reported by Pines *et al.*¹³. These alkyl cyclopentadienes may polymerise over the strong acid sites leading to the formation of carbonaceous material which deposits over the active sites reducing the activity of the catalyst. The strong tendency of the C₆ ring compounds to polymerise when in contact with acid sites is well known¹⁴.

Cesium ions in low concentrations exhibit a promoting effect (Table 2), which lies in their ability to neutralise the strong acid sites that will otherwise catalyse the undesired side reactions as described earlier.

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Synthesis of a Possible Metabolite of Trifluoperazine 2-Trifluoromethyl-7-Hydroxy-8-Methoxy-10-[3-(4-Methyl-1-Piperazinyl)-Propyl]-Phenothiazine-5-Oxide and Related Compounds

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TRIFLUOPERAZINE^{1,2}, one of the most important drug in the treatment of mental illness has been in use for the last two decades. This class of compounds possess therapeutic properties as tranquillizers, antiemetics, antihistaminics, spasmolytic and antishock agents. This initiated an interest

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